

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Immunology – Exploring Opportunities and Challenges

Workshop Chairs: Steven H. Kleinstei, Richard Scheuermann

May 28–May 29, 2024

NIAID Conference Center, Grand Hall (1D13)
5601 Fishers Lane, Rockville, MD 20852

Day 1, May 28, 2024: 8:30 a.m.–4:45 p.m.

- **Plenary Address: 8:30–8:45 a.m.**
 - Dan Rotrosen, DAIT, NIAID, NIH
 - Jeanne Marrazzo, NIAID, NIH

- **Welcome Remarks: 8:45–8:55 a.m.**
 - Richard Scheuermann, NLM, NIH
 - Steven Kleinstei, Yale University

- **Keynote: 9:00–10:00 a.m.**
 - **Toward AI Models of Human Immunity: Past, Present, Future**, John Tsang, Yale University

- **Break – 10:00–10:15 a.m.**

- **Session 1: Setting the Stage: AI Concepts and Technologies – 10:15–11:45 a.m.**
Session Chair: Laura Biven
 - **Perspectives on Artificial Intelligence from NIH**, Laura Biven, ODSS, OD, NIH
 - **AI Related Programs at NIAID**, Reed Shabman, NIAID, NIH
 - **AI Infrastructure at NIAID**, Mike Tartakovsky, NIAID, NIH
 - **Planning, Reporting, and Evaluating Research and Applications of Foundation Models**, Dina Demner-Fushman, NLM, NIH

- **Lunch Break – 11:45 a.m.–12.45 p.m.**

- **Session 2: AI Use Cases in Molecular Immunology – 12:45–2:35 p.m.**
Session Chair: Lindsay Cowell
 - **Predicting Molecular Targets of T Cell Recognition through Machine Learning**, Bjoern Peters, La Jolla Institute for Immunology
 - **Machine Learning on Adaptive Immune Receptor Repertoires for the Discovery of Disease Biomarkers and Predictors of Outcome**, Lindsay Cowell, University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center
 - **Learning the Rules of the Immune System**, Nir Hacohen, Broad Institute

- **AI for Unbiased, Interpretable Case-Control Analysis of Spatial Molecular Data**, Yakir Reshef, Harvard University
- **Panel Discussion**
- **Break – 2:35–2:45 p.m.**
- **Session 3: AI Use Cases in Cellular and Systems Immunology – 2:45–4:35 p.m.**
Session Chair: Bali Pulendran
 - **Systems Biological Assessment of the Predictors and Mechanisms of Vaccine Responses**, Bali Pulendran, Stanford University
 - **Noise Injection for Data Driven Biomarker Discovery in Multi-Omics Immune Monitoring Studies**, Brice Gaudilliere, Stanford University
 - **Multi-Omics Data Integration Using Canonical Correlation Analysis Reveals Transcriptomic Signatures Predictive of Vaccine Responses**, Richard Scheuermann, NIH
 - **Immune Signatures of Vaccination and Infection Responses**, Steven Kleinstein, Yale University
- **Panel Discussion**
- **Day 1 Closeout – 4:35–4:45 p.m.**
 - Quan Chen, NIAID, NIH

Day 2, May 29, 2024: 9:30 a.m.–4:45 p.m.

- **Welcome and Day 1 Recap – 9:30–10:00 a.m.**
 - Richard Scheuermann, NLM, NIH
 - Steven Kleinstein, Yale University
- **Session 4: AI Use Cases in Organismal Immunology – 10:00–11:30 a.m.**
Session Chair: Duygu Ucar
 - **Systems Immunology and Machine Learning in Human Immune Aging and Impaired Vaccine Responses**, Duygu Ucar, Jackson Labs
 - **Systems Immunology and Machine Learning Applications Across Human Tissues**, Peter Sims, Columbia University
 - **AI-Enabled Optimal Control for Immune Digital Twins**, Reinhard Laubenbacher, University of Florida
- **Panel Discussion**
- **Lunch Break – 11:30 a.m.–12:30 p.m.**
- **Session 5: Infrastructure – 12:30–2:20 p.m.**
Session Chair: Bjoern Peters
 - **Data Is Infrastructure – Why Quality Is Important**, Gabe Rosenfeld, NIH
 - **Using AI on ImmPort and Clinical Data Sets**, Atul Butte, University of California, San Francisco

- **Database Curation to Enhance Value for AI - IEDB and ImmuneSpace**, Bjoern Peters, La Jolla Institute for Immunology
- **Knowledge-Based AI for Immunology**, Chris Mungall, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
- **Panel Discussion**
- **Break – 2:20–2:30 p.m.**
- **Session 6: AI Use Cases in Clinical Immunology – 2:30–4.20 p.m.**
Session Chair: Vicki Shanmugam
 - **From Genes and Single Cells Back to Patient-Level Immune-Mediated Phenotypes: Opportunities and Challenges**, Katherine Liao, Harvard University
 - **AI for AI: Artificial Intelligence and Allergy/Immunology**, Supinda Bunyavanich, Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai
 - **Large Language Models for Health Care and Medicine**, Yonghui Wu, University of Florida
 - **Enabling the Next Generation of Evidence-Based Medicine with AI and Biomedical Informatics**, Chunhua Weng, Columbia University
- **Panel Discussion**
- **Wrap-Up and Closing – 4:20–4:45 p.m.**
 - Richard Scheurmann, NLM, NIH
 - Steven Kleinstein, Yale University
 - Dawei Lin, NIAID, NIH